

HISTORY OF ART

NASIREDDIN TUSI WAS A MEDIEVAL AZERBAIJANI DOCTOR AND SCIENTIST

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Abstract

The founder of the Tabriz Academy, Nasreddin Tusi, was a doctor. First of all, it can be said that he applied the statistical method in medicine. Interestingly, some parts of the Academy, founded by Tusi, were located in other cities. An example of this is the world-famous Maragha Observatory. The Maragha Observatory was built on a large plain at the height of Mount Savalan. In addition to certain laboratories, it also had a large library. According to many modern scientists, Tusi's role in the emergence of new directions in mathematics, astronomy, geometry and physics is enormous. Tusi's ethical thoughts are concentrated in his famous work, Akhlaqi-Nasiri. The academy organized by Nasreddin Tusi also had a special department for veterinary medicine. This genius scientist's work "Farajname" is dedicated to this issue. Tusi and his students studied mines, precious stones, etc. His work on is also noteworthy. Tusi's Javahirname covers these issues. These include "History of Baghdad", "Treatise on the Reflection and Refraction of Light", "Euclidean Optics", "Treatise on the Study of the Rainbow", "Book on Precious Stones", "Medical Laws", "Treatise on Public Finance", "Happy selection of days" (astrology) and other works. His works are scattered around the world. Tusi's works include History of Baghdad, Treatise on the Reflection and Refraction of Light, Euclidean Optics, Treatise on the Study of the Rainbow, Book on Precious Stones, Medical Laws, and Treatise on Society. His works are scattered around the world.

Keywords: Observatory, medicine, scientist, astronomy, academy.

People living in Azerbaijan several thousand years ago already had medical knowledge, and this stage was developing in an upward trend. In the tenth and fourteenth centuries, the Islamic world was the pinnacle of human civilization. The largest universities, observatories, hospitals, pharmacies and libraries were located in the Muslim East, where the most powerful scientists worked.

In the Middle Ages, along with the economic and cultural development of Azerbaijan, medicine also developed. One of the historical and cultural events of this period was the Maragha Observatory, founded by Nasreddin Tusi in the 13th century, and the observatory of Seyid Yahya Badgubey in Baku.

Khaja Muhammad Nasraddin Tusi was born on February 17, 1201 (597 AH) in the city of Tus in a family of tutors. The thinker's real name is Muhammad, his father's name is Muhammad, and his grandfather's name is Hasan. The people named him Nasreddin because he was an intelligent, knowledgeable and prominent scientist of his time. He adopted the nickname Tusi because he was born in Tus. Its origin is from Hamadan, one of the oldest cities in Azerbaijan. Nasreddin Tusi received his first education from his father Muhammad ibn Hasan. In his youth, he traveled to a number of major cities in the Middle East to increase his knowledge. In the introduction to his book "Seyr ve lekuk", the thinker described his childhood and wrote: "I stillAs a child, my father sent me to study with his friend, the mathematician Kamaladdin Muhammad. It was not long before my teacher left. Following my father's will, I traveled to a number of cities. Whenever I found a teacher, I took lessons from him. But I must say that I was especially interested in theology and philosophy."

In the city of Nishapur, Tusi traveled to a number of cities in the East, where he met and learned from a number of prominent scholars of the time, including Faridaddin Damad and Gutbaddin Misri. His comprehensive and in-depth knowledge soon made Muhammad famous in the scientific community. At the age of thirty, Nasreddin Mohtashem, the leader of the Kuhistan Ismailis, invited him to his palace and asked the young scholar to write a book on morality. In 1235, Nasreddin Tusi completed the famous work "Akhlaqi-Nasiri", which was later translated into a number of languages that brought him world fame. However, the ruler did not like the book and Tusi was arrested and taken to Alamut fortress. He lives in exile here. Tusi, who was deprived of the right to leave the castle, spent more than 12 years with the Ismailis, despite his unbearable moral hardships. can write several scientific works. At the end of his famous work, Sharh al-Isharat, which he completed in 1242, the scholar wrote: "I wrote many of these in the most difficult conditions. In fact, I wrote them at a time when each of them cost me a great deal of suffering and hardship. There, hell is always on fire and hot water is poured from above. There has never been a time when my eyes have not been filled with tears, my heart has not been filled with sorrow, and there has not been an hour in which my sufferings have not increased and there has not been a moment that has not brought me new excitement. Yes, one of the Persian poets rightly said: "No matter how much I look around, I see disaster in the form of a ring, and I am a precious ore in the middle of that ring. There has never been a time in my life when he was afraid of fate, not to be disappointed and sad. The judge of my eternal pleasure was care, and his soldier was excitement. O

Allah! Save me from the footsteps of the army of misfortune and from the nest of suffering. ”

In 1253, Genghis Khan's grandson Hulaki Khan marched into the Middle East. His troops also captured the invincible fortress of Alamut, freeing Nasreddin and other scholars. Nasreddin Hulaku khan is appointed personal adviser. Tusi has been thinking about the observatory for a long time. As soon as Baghdad was captured, Nasreddin asked the khan for permission to build an observatory. While discussing the construction of the famous Maragha observatory, Hulaki-khan asked the prominent mathematician and astronomer Nasreddin Tusi why it costs so much and what will be the benefit of the observatory to be built? Without answering, Tusi invited the ruler to walk near the city and said, "Let someone climb the mountain and throw an empty stone from there, but do it so that no one knows." They do so. Tas makes terrible noises on the rocks. Hulaki khan's army is terrified. At that time, Nasreddin and the khan sat quietly and watched the panic in the army. Nasreddin khan says: "Sir, we sat quietly because we knew the reason for the sound coming from the rocks. The army is excited because it does not know this. If we know in advance the nature of what is happening in the sky, there is always such peace on earth." Nasreddin's words convince Hulaki khan that he agrees to build an observatory and spends 20,000 dinars for this purpose. Later, the great scientist managed to freeze more than a hundred scientists working in the observatory. This salary was paid from taxes collected at the initiative of Nasreddin. Among the academies of Azerbaijan at that time, a large academy founded by the great Azerbaijani astrologer and physician Nasreddin

Nasreddin Tusi (1201-1274)

Many researchers consider Nasreddin Tusi to be, above all, a mathematician. His works played an important role in the development of geometry and trigonometry, not only in the East, but also in Europe. Published in Rome in 1594 and later translated into Latin, Euclid and A Description of the Beginning did much to spread Tusi's ideas in Europe. The five-volume treatise on the quadrilateral is also known as a work that played an important role in the development of trigonometry in Europe. For the first time in the history of world science, trigonometry is approached as an independent field of science. This pamphlet has been translated into English, Russian and French. Among Nasreddin's researches in the field of algebra, the method of fattening and the Binomial formula are better known. In addition, the scientist studied history, mineralogy, physics, medicine, economics, His numerous works on geography,

Tusi in Tabriz has a special place. Specialists of various disciplines took part in it. The medical field was headed by the then prominent Azerbaijani doctor Abdulmajid Tabib. Interestingly, one of his manuscripts, "Treatment with drugs" is in the Republican Manuscripts Fund. The treatment of systemic diseases attracts a lot of attention here. He was instrumental in the hospitalization and treatment of the mentally ill.

The founder of the Tabriz Academy, Nasreddin Tusi, was also a doctor. First of all, it can be said that he applied the statistical method in medicine. Interestingly, some parts of the Academy, founded by Tusi, were located in other cities. An example of this is the world-famous Maragha Observatory. The Maragha Observatory was built on a large plain at the height of Mount Savalan. In addition to certain laboratories, it also had a large library. Under Tusi's leadership, such a large observatory was built and completed in twelve years.

According to many modern scientists, Tusi's role in the emergence of new directions in mathematics, astronomy, geometry and physics is enormous. Tusi develops and completes Khayyam's ideas on mathematics. Tusi's ethical thoughts are concentrated in his famous work, Akhlaqi-Nasiri.

The academy organized by Nasreddin Tusi also had a special department for veterinary medicine. This genius scientist's work "Farajname" is dedicated to this issue. Tusi and his students studied mines, precious stones, etc. His work on is also noteworthy. Tusi's Javahirname covers these issues. The meeting of scholars organized by Nasreddin Tusi, in modern language, the presidium of the academy was located in Tabriz.

Observatory

music and, of course, astronomy are also noteworthy. These include "History of Baghdad", "Treatise on the Reflection and Refraction of Light", "Euclidean Optics", "Treatise on the Study of the Rainbow", "Book on Precious Stones", "Medical Laws", "Treatise on Public Finance", "Happy selection of days "(astrology) and other works. His works are scattered around the world. They can be found in museums and libraries in Baku, Paris, Berlin, Vienna, Oxford, Cambridge, Leipzig, Munich, Florence, Cairo, Istanbul, Moscow, St. Petersburg and Kazan. "The treatise on the study of the rainbow", "The book on precious stones", "Medical laws", "The treatise on public finance", "The choice of happy days" (astrology) and other works can be mentioned. His works are scattered around the world. They can be found in museums and libraries in Baku, Paris, Berlin,

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Many of Nasreddin's works are still awaiting their researchers.

Nasreddin Tusi wrote: "If you suffer in doing good deeds, good will remain if you suffer, if you enjoy doing bad deeds, pleasure will remain evil."

Nasreddin Tusi (1201-1274) considered morality a wealth and noted that it was not innate. He said: "If the temperament were innate, intelligent people would not advise the upbringing of their children and the purification, strengthening and habituation of the morals of young people, nor would they do so themselves."

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